

Reactivity of Pyridine. Part VIII. Bromination in Coumarins*

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Bromination¹ of several coumarins has been effected with Py-Br in presence of a free hydroxyl group, which has been found to activate the other positions vulnerable to bromination along with the 3-position. Bromination solely in 3-position requires protection of phenolic groups either as acetates⁴ or carbonates⁵; such protection, however, fails with 5-methoxy-7-acetoxycoumarins⁶.

Bromination of 4-methylumbelliferone with one mole of bromine in hot acetic acid medium was reported to take place first in the 3-position, furnishing 3-bromo-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin^{1,2}. The 4-methyl group is not affected in any case, i.e., when bromination is carried out with bromine in media like acetic acid, benzene, CCl₄, CHCl₃, CS₂, etc. NBS also fails to bring about bromination of the 4-methyl group. Seshadri and Sehgal⁷ have, however, reported that if NBS is used along with a little benzoyl peroxide, 4-methyl group can be brominated. 7-Acetoxy- and 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarins have thus been brominated to obtain 7-acetoxy- and 7-methoxy-4-bromomethylcoumarin respectively.

Bromination in 2'-hydroxychalcones⁸ has been studied, using pyridine-bromine complex⁹ (Py-Br) and found to be different from that with bromine in CCl₄, CHCl₃, CS₂, acetic acid, and benzene. Therefore, bromination of coumarin (I), 7-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin (II), 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (III), 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acetylcoumarin (IV), and 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin (V) with Py-Br was undertaken to ascertain any difference existing in the product from that obtained by normal bromination.

- (I) R₁=R₂=R₃=R₄=H.
 (II) R₁=Me; R₂=R₄=H; R₃=OCOMe.
 (III) R₁=Me; R₂=R₄=H; R₃=OH.
 (IV) R₁=Me; R₂=H; R₃=OH; R₄=COMe.
 (V) R₁=Me; R₂=Et; R₃=OH; R₄=H.

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3. Limaye, *Ber.*, 1932, **65**, 375.
4. Karrer *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, **3**, 546.
5. Fries and Nohren, *Ber.*, 1925, **58**, 1027.
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7. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, **12B**, 346.

Coumarin (I), when treated with bromine in pyridine, remained unchanged. Refluxing with NBS in benzene for 1 to 2 hr. provided the unchanged coumarin (I). 3,4-Dibromocoumarin on treatment with pyridine provided partially debrominated compound, 3-bromocoumarin, as reported¹⁰, but not a completely debrominated product as in chalcones⁸.

Compound (II) with Py-Br remained unchanged as with NBS. It is known that coumarin (II) with NBS in presence of benzoyl peroxide provides 7-acetoxy-4-bromomethyl-coumarin⁷. Use of benzoyl peroxide was of no use in presence of pyridine because pyridine reacted readily with benzoyl peroxide. So it was thought to catalyse the reaction with hydrogen peroxide. It was observed that coumarin(II) with Py-Br in presence of a few drops of H₂O₂ afforded a bromo compound, found to be identical with that obtained by Seshadri and Sehgal⁷ by the action of NBS on (II) in presence of benzoyl peroxide.

Coumarins (III), (IV), and (V), with Py-Br or with NBS in benzene yielded solely 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3,6,8-tribromocoumarin (m.p. 250°), 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acetyl-3,4-dibromocoumarin (m.p. 234-36°), and 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-3, 8-dibromocoumarin (m.p. 210-13°), respectively, and the unconverted coumarins. Identification being done by the synthesis of the respective mono, di and tri derivatives of (III) and mono and di derivatives of (IV) and (V) by bromination, as reported by earlier workers, is outlined as follows:

The above coumarins on bromination with one mole of bromine in acetic acid furnished 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-bromocoumarin (m.p. 213°), 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acetyl-3-bromocoumarin (m.p. 218°), 7-hydroxy 4-methyl-6-ethyl-3-bromocoumarin (m.p. 218°) respectively. With two moles of bromine in acetic acid (III), (IV), and (V) afforded 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3, 6- and -3,8-dibromocoumarins (m.p. 278° and 246°), 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acetyl-3, 6-dibromocoumarin (m.p. 234°), and 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-3, 8-dibromocoumarin (m. p. 210-13°) respectively. Coumarin (III), only with liquid bromine in excess, yielded 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3,6,8-tribromocoumarin¹⁻³, m.p. 250°.

Thus the reaction with Py-Br has been found to yield products similar to that obtained by the action of NBS; all the vulnerable positions for substitution are affected simultaneously. With the increase in the molar proportion of Py-Br or NBS, from one mole to two moles, the yield of the di- or tri- bromo products, as the case may be, increases and the proportion of unconverted coumarins decreases.

EXPERIMENTAL

3,4-Dibromocoumarin.—To coumarin (I), (m.p. 68°; 1.5 g.) in 60% AcOH (10 ml) was added bromine in AcOH (25% w/v, 6.4ml). The solid separating was filtered after 2hr. and crystallised from AcOH (dil.), m.p. 101° (lit. m.p. 101-102°), yield 1.0g.

Action of Pyridine on 3,4-Dibromocoumarin.—3,4-Dibromocoumarin (1 g.) was treated with pyridine (10 ml) in cold or the solution was just brought to boiling after addition of pyridine. The solution was diluted with water and acidified with HCl. The

solid obtained was crystallised from AcOH (dil.), m.p. 110°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: Br, 35.2. Calc. Br, 35.4%).

Action of Pyridine-bromine Complex on Coumarin (I).—To (I) (1g.) in pyridine (10 ml) was added bromine (0.5 ml) and the mixture was kept overnight. In another experiment, it was refluxed for 5 to 10 min. In both the cases the solution was diluted with water and acidified with HCl. A solid obtained on crystallisation was the unconverted coumarin (yield 1.2 g.).

Action of Pyridine-bromine Complex on (II).—Coumarin (II) (m.p. 152°; 1g.) was dissolved in pyridine (10 ml) and 2 or 3 drops of hydrogen peroxide were added to it (without H₂O₂ bromination did not take place). Bromine (0.5 ml) was added and the solution was kept for 1 hr., acidified with HCl, and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried with anhydrous CaCl₂ and evaporated. The solid obtained was crystallised from AcOH (dil.), m.p. 183°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: Br, 28.4%). It showed no depression in m.p. when admixed with 7-acetoxy-4-bromomethylcoumarin, obtained by the action of NBS in presence of benzoyl peroxide on (II).

Action of Py-Br on (III), (IV), and (V).—Coumarin (III, m.p. 184°), (IV, m.p. 168°), or (V, m.p. 212°) was dissolved in pyridine (10 ml) and bromine (in one molar proportion in CCl₄ or without CCl₄) was slowly added to it. The solution was warmed (or kept cold for 15 min). The solution was diluted with water and the solid separating was filtered and crystallised from EtOH (dil.) and AcOH. Coumarin (III) furnished a compound, m.p. 250° (AcOH) which showed no depression in mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3,6,8-tribromocoumarin. (Found: Br, 57.8. Calc., Br, 57.1%). (IV) provided a compound, m.p. 234-36° (AcOH), sparingly soluble in EtOH; the mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-acetyl-3,6-dibromocoumarin remained underpressed. (Found: Br, 42.4. Calc. Br, 42.6%). (V) gave rise to a compound, m.p. 210-13° (AcOH), remaining underpressed with 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl-3,8-dibromocoumarin¹².

Using two moles of bromine in the above experiment, the yields of the respective products increased and the proportion of the unconverted coumarins (dil. EtOH) decreased.

Action of NBS on (III), (IV), and (V).—Coumarin (III), (IV), or (V) and NBS in benzene (30 ml per 0.01 ml) were refluxed for 2 hr. Benzene was removed and the residue was washed with hot water. The solid was crystallised fractionally from EtOH and AcOH.

¹²Results found were similar to that obtained in case of Py-Br. Increase in the proportion of NBS increased the yield of the respective bromo compounds.

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